

ADDITION PRODUCTS OF ANILS WITH SOME METALLIC CHLORIDES

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It is observed that ethyl acetoacetate and aniline when treated with fused zinc chloride give a crystalline addition product, ethyl acetoacetate-anil-zinc chloride, which is also obtained from ethyl acetoacetate-anil and zinc chloride. The addition product can be decomposed by sodium carbonate to get the anil. No such addition product of an anil is known in literature. Anil of ethyl α -methylacetoacetate and *o*- and *p*-methyl- and *o*-methoxy-anils of ethyl acetoacetate gave similar crystalline addition products with zinc chloride. Similar addition products were also obtained from the above anils with cadmium and mercuric chlorides. Acetophenone-anil and benzaldehyde-anil did not give an addition product but got hydrolysed. This property of β -ketonic ester-anils can be used as a qualitative test for their detection or to separate them from a mixture or to obtain them in a pure form.

It is well known that ethyl acetoacetate reacts with aniline in two ways: Equimolecular proportions of both, when mixed and kept at room temperature, furnish the anil, with elimination of water (Conrad and Limpach, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 944, 948). On the other hand, if aniline is slowly added to ethyl acetoacetate at 160°, acetoacetanilide is formed, alcohol being eliminated (Knorr, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 772). The anil of ethyl acetoacetate at 280° furnishes 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline (Conrad and Limpach, *loc. cit.*); while the anilide on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid gives 2-hydroxy-4-methylquinoline (Knorr, *Annalen*, 1888, 245, 358, *et. seq.*).

In course of some synthetic work for preparing these hydroxyquinoline derivatives, fused zinc chloride was tried as a condensing agent for the reaction of aniline and ethyl acetoacetate. On working up, a well defined crystalline product was obtained which melted above 240° over a wide range and with decomposition. It decomposed on long exposure to air or in boiling water, smell of aniline being perceptible; with boiling alkali, aniline was formed. The usual qualitative tests showed the presence of zinc and halogen.

To determine the identity of the product aniline, ethyl acetoacetate-anil and acetoacetic anilide were separately treated with equimolecular amounts of zinc chloride. Aniline and the anil gave colorless addition products. The anilide was recovered unchanged. The addition product of aniline and zinc chloride differed considerably in properties from the above compound; while that from the anil resembled in all its properties to this compound. Thus, the substance under investigation appeared to be an addition product of the anil and zinc chloride. The results of analysis showed the presence of equimolecular proportions of the anil and zinc chloride. The substance, when treated with sodium carbonate, decomposed to give the anil which could be converted by Limpach's method (*Ber.*, 1931, 64, 969) into 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline. Hence, the substance under investigation was an addition product of ethyl acetoacetate-anil and zinc chloride, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{N}:\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{CH}_2\text{CO}\cdot\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5\cdot\text{ZnCl}_2$. Ethyl acetoacetate and aniline reacted in presence of fused zinc chloride to give the anil (cf. Reddelein, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4759; 1910, 43, 2476, 2480, *et. seq.*), which then formed an addition product with zinc chloride. No such addition product of an anil appears to be known in literature. The same addition product can be obtained in a purer state by mixing the anil and zinc chloride in rectified spirit solution.

Ethyl α -methylacetoacetate-anil also gave an addition product with zinc chloride, which was also obtained from ethyl α -methylacetoacetate, aniline and fused zinc chloride. On decomposition with sodium carbonate solution it gave the anil which could be converted into 4-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylquinoline. Various substituted anils, viz., *o*- and *p*-methyl- and *o*-methoxy-anils of ethyl acetoacetate gave similar crystalline addition products.

Similar addition products were also obtained from these anils with mercury and cadmium chlorides. Attempts were made to get such addition products from acetophenone-anil and benzaldehyde-anil. However, these anils got hydrolysed in presence of zinc chloride and aniline-zinc chloride was obtained.

Thus, the formation of additive products with the above metallic chlorides appears to be the property of anils of β -ketonic ester and can be used as a qualitative test for distinguishing these anils, or separating them from a mixture or getting them in a pure form.

EXPERIMENTAL

Addition Product of Ethyl Acetoacetate-anil and Zinc Chloride

(1) Ethyl acetoacetate (4.3 g.), aniline (3.1 g.) and powdered fused zinc chloride (4.6 g.) were mixed. Considerable heat was evolved. It was heated on a steam-bath for two hours, water was added and the product washed thoroughly. It was crystallised from rectified spirit, in colorless prismatic needles (3.5 g.). It shrank at about 190° and melted in a range of 248°-255° with decomposition. (Found : Cl, 21.1. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N.ZnCl_2$ requires Cl, 20.8 per cent).

(2) Ethyl acetoacetate-anil (Cavallito and Haskell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1166) (3.4 g.) and powdered zinc chloride (2.3 g.) were mixed and heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours. On working up, the above product of m.p. 239°-45° was obtained.

(3) The anil (3.4 g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit (7 c.c.) and a solution of zinc chloride in minimum amount of the same solvent added. Fine crystals of the product separated. The mixture was kept aside for some time and the crystals collected when the same product was obtained.

Ethyl acetoacetate-anil-zinc chloride has no sharp and definite melting point. It shrinks and appears to start melting at 190°, turns blackish at about 205° and actually melts between 230° and 260°. The melting point is found to vary in this range in different preparations. It starts decomposing at about 255°. On exposure to air the crystals slowly change colour to yellowish and then pinkish and there is a strong smell of aniline. It decomposes with hot water or dilute alkali giving aniline. Cold dilute hydrochloric acid has little effect. It is difficultly soluble in ethyl alcohol, acetone and acetic acid in cold, but dissolves quite readily on boiling. It is insoluble in other usual organic solvents.

Decomposition of Ethyl Acetoacetate-anil-zinc Chloride with Sodium Carbonate

The anil-zinc chloride (1 g.) was suspended in rectified spirit and sodium carbonate added, and the mixture well shaken when zinc carbonate precipitated. It was kept for about two hours, filtered and the filtrate extracted with ether. The extract was dried and ether removed. The oil that remained was found to be ethyl acetoacetate-anil as, (i) it did not dissolve easily in dilute hydrochloric acid, (ii) it gave the addition product with zinc chloride, and (iii) it could be converted into 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline, m.p. 230° by Conrad and Limpach's method (*loc. cit.* cf. Hughes and Louis, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1938, **71**, 458).

Addition Product of Aniline and Zinc Chloride

Aniline (3.1 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit was mixed with a solution of zinc chloride (2.3 g.) in the same solvent. Soon colorless plates of aniline-zinc chloride separated, m.p. above 220° with decomposition. (Found : Cl, 22.1. $2C_6H_7N.ZnCl_2$ requires Cl, 22.2 per cent). On exposure to air it turns pinkish giving a strong smell of aniline. It decomposes with hot water or dilute alkali. It is readily soluble in alcohol, acetone or acetic acid in cold, and insoluble in other usual organic solvents.

Several other addition products were prepared from various anils with zinc, cadmium and mercuric chlorides. The general method used was the same, namely, mixing equimolecular proportions of the two in rectified spirit solution when they separated as well defined crystals melting above 200° within a range and with decomposition, there being no sharp and definite melting point. In solubilities and other properties also they resemble ethyl acetoacetate-anil-zinc chloride. For the sake of brevity they are tabulated below.

TABLE I

No.	Anils.	Metallic chloride.	Product.	Shape of crystals.	M. p.	Chlorine	
						Found.	Calc.
1	Ethyl acetoacetate-anil	CdCl ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N, CdCl ₂	Colorless tiny needles	>220° (decomp.)	18.0%	18.3%
2	Do	HgCl ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N, HgCl ₂	Colorless columns	>120° (decomp.)	15.0	14.9
3	Ethyl α-methylacetoacetate-anil (a)	ZnCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, ZnCl ₂ (b)	Colorless prismatic needles	248-58° (decomp.)	19.8	20.0
4	Do	HgCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, HgCl ₂	Colorless needles	145-75° (decomp.)	14.7	14.5
5	Ethyl acetoacetate-o-methylanil (c)	ZnCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, ZnCl ₂	Slender needles	>230° (decomp.)	20.4	20.0
6	Do	CdCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, CdCl ₂	Tiny silky needles	>220° (decomp.)	17.5	17.7
7	Ethyl acetoacetate-p-methylanil (c)	ZnCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, ZnCl ₂	Tiny needles	>230° (decomp.)	20.1	20.0
8	Do	CdCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N, CdCl ₂	Fine needles	>220° (decomp.)	17.9	17.7
9	Ethyl acetacetate-o-methoxyanil(d)	ZnCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N, ZnCl ₂	Colorless needles	>220° (decomp.)	19.0	19.1
10	Do	CdCl ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N, CdCl ₂	Colorless tiny needles	>220° (decomp.)	17.2	17.0
11	Acetophenone-anil (e)	ZnCl ₂	C ₆ H ₅ HN ₂ , ZnCl ₂ (f)	Colorless plates	>220° (decomp.)	—	—
12	Benzaldehyde-anil (g)	ZnCl ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂ , ZnCl ₂ (h)	Colorless plates	>220° (decomp.)	—	—

(a) Conrad and Limpach, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 2990.

(b) Also prepared from ethyl α-methylacetoacetate, aniline and zinc chloride. On decomposition by sodium carbonate it gave back the anil which could be converted by Limpach's method into 4-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylquinoline (Wohnlich, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1913, **251**, 535).

(c) Conrad and Limpach, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 523.

(d) *Idem, ibid.*, p. 1649.

(e) Reddelein, *ibid.*, 1910, **43**, 2478.

(f) A strong smell of acetophenone developed when the reactants were mixed. The product on decomposition gave only aniline (isolated as hydrochloride, m.p. 196-97°), no acetophenone being isolated.

(g) Organic Synthesis, Col. Vol. I, p. 80.

(h) A strong smell of benzaldehyde developed in the mixture. The product on decomposition gave only aniline (hydrochloride, m.p. 198°), no benzaldehyde could be isolated.